

Some Observations on Selenium and Selenium Dioxide and the Oxides of Nitrogen.

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No observations appear to have been recorded on the action of NO on Se or SeO_2 , nor on the reactions between NO_2 , and Se and SeO_2 , except the one referred to in section III. The following observations, made by the author, may therefore be worth putting on record.

I. *Selenium Dioxide and Nitric Oxide.*

Selenium dioxide is fairly easily reduced to elementary selenium, and so it often behaves as a mild oxidising agent. It was expected, therefore, that it would react with nitric oxide. The subject was studied experimentally as follows. A long glass tube, of about 1.5 cm. bore and constricted at about the middle, was sealed on to a vacuum tap at one end. Some selenium was placed in the open half of the tube and oxidised to SeO_2 by heating in a stream of dry oxygen which was mixed with some dry NO_2 , obtained by heating dry lead nitrate contained in a side-tube. Some of the SeO_2 was then sublimed into the other part of the tube, and the tube was drawn off and sealed at the constriction. This procedure was adopted because of the highly hygroscopic nature of SeO_2 . After closing the tap, this tube was sealed on to an all-glass apparatus consisting of a Töpler pump and mercury gas-holder containing dry nitric oxide. After completely evacuating the tube containing the SeO_2 , it was filled with NO at atmospheric pressure. No immediate reaction occurred, and after leaving for a week at room temperature (30° .) the gas remained colourless and the white needles of SeO_2 remained unchanged. The tube was then slowly heated, but no reaction occurred up to the sublimation temperature of SeO_2 (about 315° .) It was found that SeO_2 could be sublimed unchanged in an atmosphere of nitric oxide. During sublimation the SeO_2 gave its characteristic greenish-yellow vapour, but as soon as this had condensed, the gas in the tube was seen to be colourless and the sublimate was snow-white. The gas was pumped out of the tube and found to be unchanged NO.

II. *Selenium and Nitric Oxide.*

A tube of about 50 c.c. capacity, closed at one end and sealed on to a vacuum tap at the other, was sealed on to the Töpler pump and mercury gas-holder containing NO. The tube contained 2.3 g. of dry amorphous selenium. The Se was prepared, by passing SO₂ into a solution of pure selenious acid to which some HCl had been added, filtering, washing repeatedly with water, and drying in *vacuo* over concentrated H₂SO₄. The tube was evacuated completely, heated in an electric tube-furnace, and filled with NO. Several experiments were carried out and it was found that no reaction took place between selenium and nitric oxide up to a temperature of 330°. After several hours at this temperature, the selenium had distilled to the cooler end of the tube and condensed there as opaque black drops. After the experiments, the gas was pumped out and found to be unchanged NO by absorption by Diver's reagent (alkaline sulphite solution). Experiments were not carried out at higher temperatures as, with the arrangement used, the selenium would have simply distilled into the connecting tube outside the heater.

III. *Selenium and Nitrogen Tetroxide.*

The only reference to this subject that has been found is in a paper by Jannek and Meyer (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2876). These workers, for determination of atomic weight, prepared pure SeO₂ by passing a stream of oxygen mixed with some NO₂ over heated selenium. It has been known since the time of Barzelius' investigations on selenium that selenium is oxidised by oxygen much more readily in the presence of nitric acid vapour. Jannek and Meyer (*loc. cit.*) explain this as being due to a reaction similar to that taking place in the Lead Chamber Process, the NO acting as oxygen-carrier. In support of this view they state that they had found that when NO₂ is led over powdered Se, it is reduced to NO, but they give no experimental details except that the reaction occur at ordinary temperatures and better at higher temperatures well below the melting point of selenium.

A series of experiments was carried out in order to investigate this reaction. Owing to the nonavailability of liquid air, the arrangement described below was used. Dry liquid nitrogen tetroxide was sealed into a number of small capsules which were drawn out to fine

capillaries at one end. The NO_2 was prepared by Cundall's method. One arm of a T-piece was fused to a closed glass tube of about 200 c.c. capacity. This tube contained several grams of dry amorphous selenium spread along its length and it was supported in a horizontal position. Another arm of the T-piece was fused on to a tap (A) which led through a tube of powdered NaOH to the Töpler pump. The third arm of the T-piece was also fused on to a tap (B). This tap was placed in the "open" position and one of the capsules of NO_2 was introduced into its open end so that the capillary of the capsule passed into the bore in the key of the tap. The open end of the tap was then drawn off and sealed after introducing some glass-wool to prevent the capsule from becoming heated. In order to prevent the possibility of the NO_2 acting on tap-grease, the taps were lubricated with gummy metaphosphoric acid which was protected from atmospheric moisture by an external layer of vaseline. After completely evacuating, tap A was closed and by slightly turning tap B, the capillary end of the NO_2 capsule was broken off and the nitrogen tetroxide rapidly vaporised into the reaction vessel containing the selenium, which was kept at 30° . No visible signs of action were seen on first contact. By observing the colour of the gas at intervals, as seen through a layer 25 cm. thick against a white background, a slow fading of colour was found to occur, and after 48 hours the gas had become quite colourless. The gas was then pumped out and analysed. It was found to be practically pure nitric oxide. The contents of the reaction tube were now treated with water to dissolve out the SeO_2 formed. This solution was filtered and treated with SO_2 to decompose the selenious acid, and the precipitated Se was collected in a Gooch crucible and weighed. The figures obtained in one of these experiments are as follows

	Found.	Calculated.
Weight of NO_2 used	0.302	0.293
Weight of Se collected	0.252	0.252
Volume of NO at N.T.P.	141.2 c.c.	142.7 c.c.

The volume of NO stated is the volume of gas absorbed by the alkaline sulphite. 0.77 C.c. remained unabsorbed; this may have been nitrogen formed by complete reduction of NO_2 . The values given in the second column are calculated from the equation

The approximate agreement of these numbers with those found shows that this equation represents the reaction that occurs to the extent of about 97 per cent. The result recorded in section I shows that this reaction is not reversible within the temperature range mentioned.

The reaction of selenium with liquid nitrogen tetroxide was also studied. Some liquid nitrogen tetroxide was prepared by Cundall's method, purified by being passed through tubes containing heated As_4O_6 and anhydrous CuO , and dried by P_2O_5 . It was then distilled over P_2O_5 into a stoppered tube through a side arm which was then drawn off and sealed. This tube was kept at 0° by placing it in a vacuum flask containing ice and water. On adding some dry amorphous selenium, the light yellow liquid became slightly green. After some minutes, it was bright green and after several hours greenish blue. The tube was kept at 0° for several days. No effervescence was observed and no noticeable pressure was generated, indicating that no appreciable amount of nitrogen was formed. The tube was then allowed to warm and the oxides of nitrogen to escape. The residue consisted of SeO_2 with an appreciable amount of unchanged Se. On treating with water and filtering, a solution of selenious acid free from selenic acid was obtained. This experiment shows that the reaction between selenium and liquid nitrogen tetroxide may be represented by the equation

IV. *Selenium Dioxide and Nitrogen Tetroxide.*

The experiments described in the previous section indicate that the reaction between selenium and nitrogen tetroxide takes place slowly. The slowness of the reaction is probably not due to the reaction itself but to the layer of SeO_2 that soon covers the surface of the selenium and prevents further contact. This layer of SeO_2 is apparently insoluble in liquid nitrogen tetroxide as the following experiment shows. Some SeO_2 was sublimed in to the bottom of a U-tube, one arm of which was sealed, and then some nitrogen tetroxide was condensed in it. After placing a plug of glass-wool halfway down the open arm of the U-tube, it was sealed off. After leaving the SeO_2 and liquid NO_2 in contact for 24 hours, the U-tube was inverted so as to filter the liquid through the glass wool into one closed end of the

U-tube. The other end of the U-tube was now cooled in a freezing mixture so as to cause the NO_2 to distil over. The process was hastened by slight warming. No residue of SeO_2 remained after the NO_2 had distilled over. There was no indication that these two compounds combine to form a double compound.

V. *Selenium and Nitric Acid.*

It is well-known that the oxidising action of ordinary nitric acid on elements is, in some cases, due to the catalytic action of NO_2 present as an impurity. The pure acid is often without action, as in the case of copper. It was thought that this might be the case with selenium as it has been shown that Se is acted upon by NO_2 . Some of the purest obtainable strong nitric acid was treated with 5 per cent. of its weight of urea so as to remove any NO_2 present. When some amorphous selenium was added to this acid, there was an immediate and vigorous reaction. Nitric acid therefore appears to react with selenium in the absence of nitrogen tetroxide.

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